

Topology-acidity-catalytic activity interplay in hierarchical nanolayered aluminosilicate zeolites for Friedel-Crafts alkylation

Oleksiy V. Shvets^a, Mykhailo M. Kurmach^a, Michal Mazur^b, Petr Golis^b, Pavlo S. Yaremov^a, Oleg Petrov^c, Nataliya D. Shcherban^a, Jiří Čejka^{b,*}, Mariya V. Shamzhy^{b,*}

^a L.V. Piszarzhenskii Institute of Physical Chemistry, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, 31 pr. Nauky, Kyiv 03028, Ukraine

^b Department of Physical and Macromolecular Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Hlavova 8, Prague 2 12840, Czech Republic

^c Department of Low Temperature Physics, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, V Holešovičkách 747/2, Prague 8 180 00, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Nanolayered zeolites
Acid sites
Friedel-Crafts alkylation

ABSTRACT

Nanolayered zeolites are at the forefront of research as efficient catalysts for reactions involving bulky molecules. To date, various zeolites have been synthesized in nanolayered form via direct hydrothermal crystallization using Gemini-type surfactants, and their enhanced catalytic performance has been demonstrated in acid-catalyzed transformations of bulky substrates. However, the influence of zeolite topology on the strength and coordination environment of surface acid sites and its effect on catalytic behavior remains insufficiently understood. This study explores topology-acidity-activity relationships using a series of nanolayered aluminosilicate zeolites with FER, MFI, MOR, and BEA topologies in the alkylation of mesitylene with benzyl alcohol as a surface-acid-site-sensitive model reaction. *In situ* FTIR-monitored thermodesorption of substituted pyridines showed comparable surface Brønsted acid strength across the zeolites, while ²⁷Al MAS NMR spectroscopy revealed a topology-dependent increase in fraction of distorted tetrahedral Al sites: MFI (21 %) < FER (30 %) < MOR (57 %) < BEA (64 %). Catalytic activity increased with surface-accessible Brønsted acid site concentration (mmol/g) or density (mmol/m²) in nanolayered MFI, FER, and MOR, with FER showing the highest yield (37 %) and selectivity (84 %). This trend was disrupted in BEA, which, despite the reasonably high surface Brønsted acid site concentration, showed lower activity. The findings of this study highlight the impact of topology-dependent structural features on catalytic performance of nanolayered zeolites.

1. Introduction

Zeolites are among the most widely used heterogeneous catalysts for acid-base processes due to their high thermal stability, uniformity of intracrystalline micropores, and the presence of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites [1,2]. The intrinsic microporosity of zeolites makes them highly effective shape-selective catalysts in oil refining, petrochemical processes, and fine chemical synthesis [3]. However, the same feature imposes internal mass transport limitations, particularly in reactions involving bulky molecules. Therefore, zeolites with hierarchical micro-mesoporosity have attracted increasing interest [4–6], as they reduce diffusion limitations for bulky molecules accessing active sites. Such zeolites can be synthesized via various methods, including delamination, structure-directing agent (SDA)-assisted hydrothermal synthesis, and seed-induced hydrothermal crystallization [7–9].

Among the reported synthesis methods, SDA-assisted hydrothermal

crystallization is the most promising approach for preparing nanolayered zeolites of different topologies with hierarchical porosity [10, 11]. The use of "soft" SDAs, such as organic poly-quaternary ammonium salts and Gemini-type surfactants has proven particularly effective for producing zeolite catalysts with high external surface areas (exceeding 600 m²/g) and large mesopore volumes (up to 1.5 cm³/g) [12–15]. Gemini-type surfactants consist of hydrophilic and hydrophobic parts. The hydrophilic part typically includes two or more quaternary ammonium groups connected by short alkyl chains (4–6 carbon atoms) and plays a templating role by promoting zeolite crystallization. The hydrophobic tails usually contain alkyl chains with more than eight carbon atoms, which restrict crystal growth in specific crystallographic directions favoring the formation of zeolite nanorod or nanosheets [12, 16–19]. These zeolites exhibiting broad mesopore size distributions emerged as active catalysts for methanol-to-hydrocarbons process [20], the Friedel-Crafts alkylation [21–23] and acylation [24], Beckmann

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: jiri.cejka@natur.cuni.cz (J. Čejka), mariya.shamzhy@natur.cuni.cz (M.V. Shamzhy).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115580>

Received 16 July 2025; Received in revised form 17 September 2025; Accepted 27 September 2025

Available online 30 September 2025

0920-5861/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

rearrangement [25], annulation of phenols [18,26], Prins cyclization [15,27], among others.

The acidic properties of nanolayered zeolites have been investigated using IR and NMR spectroscopies with adsorbed probe molecules [10, 28,29], as well as potentiometric titration [30], all demonstrating the decrease in average strength of acid sites compared to conventional microcrystalline zeolites.

In zeolite science, the term “zeolite topology” refers to the three-dimensional connectivity pattern of the tetrahedral framework atoms (T = Si, Al, etc.) independently of the chemical composition or crystal size of a zeolite [31,32]. Each unique topology is assigned a three-letter framework type code (e.g., MFI, FER, MOR, BEA) by the International Zeolite Association Structure Commission [31]. While the role of zeolite topology has been recognized in acid-catalyzed transformations over conventional microcrystalline zeolites [33–35], its influence on the strength and state of surface acid sites in nanolayered zeolites and the resulting effect on their catalytic behavior, remains largely unexplored. Previous studies have mainly focused on either introducing hierarchical porosity into zeolites using various synthesis approaches or on tuning acidity *via* isomorphous substitution of Al with other tri- or tetravalent elements [2], without systematically disentangling the relationship between framework topology, surface acidity, and catalytic behavior.

This contribution addresses this knowledge gap by employing a Gemini-type SDA-based synthetic strategy to prepare hierarchical nanolayered zeolites with FER, MFI, MOR, and BEA topologies as thin nanosheets (2 – 40 nm thick). This well-defined set of zeolite materials enables a systematic study of how the framework topology of nanolayered zeolites shapes the characteristics of surface acid sites (i.e., strength, coordination environment), and how these topology-driven acidity characteristics influence catalytic performance in surface-acid-site-sensitive Friedel-Crafts alkylation of mesitylene with benzyl alcohol. The nature and strength of acid sites were assessed by *in situ* FTIR spectroscopy of pyridine complemented by potentiometric titration, while surface-accessible Brønsted acid sites were selectively probed using bulky 2,6-di-*tert*-butylpyridine and 2,4,6-tri-*tert*-butylpyridine. Topology-dependent variations in Al coordination were documented by ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectroscopy, while *in situ* FTIR spectroscopy revealed that the strength of surface Brønsted acid sites was largely topology-independent. Overall, the results demonstrate that topology-dependent structural features modulate the state of surface acid sites, which in turn have impact on the catalytic behavior of nanolayered zeolites.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Materials and methods

Synthesis of SDAs. Two Gemini-type surfactants, SDA1 and SDA2, were used as SDAs for the preparation of nanolayered zeolites (Scheme 1). They were prepared following modified procedures described in

detail in Ref. [18,36].

SDA1. For the preparation of SDA1, 0.5 mol of 4,4'-trimethylene-bis(1-methylpiperidine) (Sigma-Aldrich, 99 %) and 1 mol of octadecyl bromide (ABCR, 99 %) were mixed in a 1:1 (v/v) mixture of acetonitrile (Enamine, 95 +%) and benzene (Enamine, 95 +%). The reaction mixture was stirred at 80 °C for 2 – 3 days. After completion of the reaction, the formed yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with methyl *tert*-butyl ether (MTBE, Enamine, 95 +%) and dried under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. The product was obtained in 75 % yield (0.35 mol) and its purity confirmed by ^1H NMR.

SDA2. The detailed procedure for SDA2 synthesis was described in Ref. [37]. This SDA was obtained using N-hexadecyldimethylbromohexylammonium bromide ($\text{C}_{16-6-\text{Br}}$) and N-hexadecyldimethyldimethylaminohexyl ammonium bromide $\text{C}_{16-6-\text{N}}(\text{CH}_3)_2$. $\text{C}_{16-6-\text{Br}}$ was prepared by the following protocol. 3 mol of 1,6-dibromohexane (TCI, 95 +%) was dissolved in 200 mL of 1,4-dioxane (Enamine, 95 +%) – benzene (Enamine, 95 +%) mixture (1/1 vol). 1 mol of N-hexadecyldimethylamine (TCI, 97 %) was dissolved in 150 – 200 mL of 1, 4-dioxane – benzene mixture. N-hexadecyldimethylamine solution was added dropwise to the first solution during 2 – 3 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 – 4 days, and then the solvents were evaporated. A white solid was collected, washed with MTBE, and dried. 0.9 mol of $\text{C}_{16-6-\text{Br}}$ was obtained.

$\text{C}_{16-6-\text{N}}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ was obtained using the following procedure. 3 mol of N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-1,6-diaminohexane (TCI, 99 %) was dissolved in a mixture of acetonitrile – 1,4-dioxane (1:1). The solution containing 1 mol of 1-bromohexadecane (ABCR, 99 %) in 250 mL of acetonitrile – 1,4-dioxane (1:1) mixture was added dropwise to the above solution. The reaction mixture was kept under stirring at 80 °C for 4 days, cooled, evaporated, the precipitate was filtered, washed with MTBE, and dried. Ca. 0.62 mol of $\text{C}_{16-6-\text{NH}}$ (62 % yield) was obtained. In the last step, 0.5 mol of $\text{C}_{16-6-\text{NH}}$ and 0.5 mol of $\text{C}_{16-6-\text{Br}}$ were dissolved in acetonitrile – dioxane (1:1) mixture, heated under reflux, and kept for 24 h. The mixture was evaporated and the precipitate was filtered, washed with MTBE and dried. 0.4 mol of SDA2 (a yield of 80 %, the purity was confirmed by ^1H NMR) was obtained.

2.1.1. Synthesis of nanolayered zeolites FER, BEA, MOR

Hierarchical zeolites with FER, BEA, and MOR topologies were synthesized using SDA1 according to the procedure published in Ref. [15]. The optimal molar composition of reaction mixture for each zeolite topology are summarized in Table 1. Typically, the aluminium isopropoxide (Fluka, 98 %) or $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \times 18 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Aldrich, 98 %) were subjected to hydrolysis in an aqueous solution of SDA1 and sodium hydroxide (Lach-Ner, 99 %) in a Nalgen® bottle. Then tetraethylorthosilicate (Aldrich, 98 %) was added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 20 min in a closed bottle. Ethanol was added to the resulting mixture and stirred at 65 °C for 16 – 18 h. The resulting hot gel was quickly loaded into a Teflon-lined autoclave and heated at

Scheme 1. Gemini-type surfactants used as SDAs for the preparation of nanolayered zeolites.

Table 1

The composition of the reaction mixtures for the synthesis of nanolayered zeolites.

Sample	SDA	Molar composition in reaction mixture			SDA	H ₂ O	EtOH	τ , days	Si/Al _{in} the sample
		SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O					
MOR	1	24	0.9 ^a	5.7	1.8	1706	192	13	9.2
BEA	1	30	1.5 ^b	7.5	1.8	2132	240	10	9.1
FER	1	30	1.5 ^b	8.9	1.8	2132	240	14	7.9
MFI	2	30	0.3 ^a	6.8	1.0	1070	120	10	27.7

^a aluminum isopropoxide used as Al source^b Al₂(SO₄)₃ × 18 H₂O used as Al source

150 °C for 10 – 14 days under stirring (~ 60 rpm). The obtained solids were filtered, washed thoroughly with distilled water and ethanol, and then dried overnight at 80 – 100 °C. To remove the SDA1, the as-synthesized zeolites were calcined in air at 600 °C for 5 h (5 °C/min).

2.1.2. Synthesis of nanolayered zeolite MFI

The synthesis of nanolayered MFI zeolite was performed according to the procedure published in Ref. [12]. The molar composition of the reaction mixture was 30SiO₂ : 0.3Al₂O₃ : 6.8Na₂O : 1.0SDA2 : 1070 H₂O : 120 C₂H₅OH (Table 1). Typically, aluminium isopropoxide (Fluka, 98 %) was added to an aqueous solution of SDA2 and sodium hydroxide (Lach-Ner, 99 %) in a Nalgen® bottle. The reaction mixture was heated to 60 °C for 1 h under stirring. Subsequently, tetraethylorthosilicate (Aldrich, 98 %) was added and the mixture was stirred at 60 °C for 1 h in a closed bottle. The resulting gel was quickly loaded into a Teflon-lined autoclave and heated at 150 °C for 10 days under stirring (~ 60 rpm). The obtained solid was filtered, washed with distilled water and ethanol, and then dried overnight at 80 – 100 °C. To remove SDA2, the as-synthesized zeolite was calcined in air at 550 °C for 5 h (5 °C/min).

To obtain the H-forms of the nanolayered zeolites, the calcined powders (0.5 g) were stirred in 30 mL of 1 M ammonium chloride solution at 40 °C for 16 – 18 h. The resulting materials were thoroughly washed with distilled water to remove excess ammonium chloride and then dried. The ion exchange was repeated twice, followed by final calcination at 450 – 500 °C.

Microcrystalline commercial zeolites FER (CP914 C), MFI (CBV8014), MOR (CBV 21 A) and BEA (CBV 811E) have been purchased from Zeolyst, transformed to H-form using the above-described procedure, characterized as reported in Ref. [38,39] and used for comparative ²⁷Al NMR spectroscopic studies.

2.2. Characterization

The phase composition and purity of the zeolites were verified using X-ray diffractometer "D8 ADVANCE" ("Bruker") with CuK_α-radiation ($\lambda = 1.542$ nm) in the range of $2\theta = 5^\circ - 45^\circ$ with a step of $2\theta = 0.05^\circ$ and a signal accumulation of 3 s/step.

The textural characteristics of zeolites were determined using nitrogen physisorption. Nitrogen adsorption isotherms were measured at -196 °C by a volumetric method with a Sorptomatic-1990 porous material analyzer. The external surface area and micropore volume were calculated by the *t*-plot method [40]. The specific surface area was evaluated using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) equation [41]. The mesopore size distribution was determined using the Barnett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method [42].

The elemental composition of the catalysts was analyzed using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS; Thermo-Scientific iCAP 7000). For sample digestion, 50 mg of zeolite was placed in a closed vessel along with 1.8 mL of HF, 5.4 mL of HCl, and 1.8 mL of HNO₃. The mixture was heated in a microwave digestion system to ensure complete dissolution. After cooling, 16 mL of H₃BO₃ was added to neutralize excess HF, and the solution was subjected to a second heating step in the microwave.

The crystal morphology of the obtained materials was studied using

electron microscopies. SEM images were obtained using JEOL JSM-IT800 and a Thermo Fisher Scientific Scios 2 DualBeam FIB-SEM microscopes using secondary and backscattered electron detectors. The sample was ground and spread over carbon tape. Images were acquired at an accelerating voltage of 1–3 kV, a beam current of 10 – 50 pA, and a working distance up to 10 mm.

STEM imaging was carried out using a JEOL JEM NEOARM-200F microscope equipped with a Schottky-type field emission gun (FEG) and a TVIPS XF416 CMOS camera. Samples were prepared by directly depositing zeolite crystals onto a holey carbon film supported on a 300-mesh copper TEM grid. Due to the beam sensitivity of the materials, imaging was performed under low electron dose conditions. Microscope alignment was calibrated using a standard gold nanoparticle reference. STEM images were acquired in annular dark-field (ADF) mode.

The concentration and strength of acid sites and their distribution among internal and external surface of nanolayered zeolites were studied using FTIR-monitored thermodesorption of probe molecules with different kinetic diameters: pyridine (Py, 0.57 nm [43]), 2, 6-di-tert-butylpyridine (DTBPy, 0.79 nm [44]), and 2,4,6-tri-tert-butylpyridine (TTBPy, 1.1 nm [44]). The FTIR experiments were performed following the recently revisited transmission-mode protocol for quantitative analysis of acidity in zeolites [43]. Infrared spectra were collected at room temperature (128 scans and resolution of 4 cm⁻¹) using a Nicolet™ iS50 FTIR spectrometer and processed with OMNIC software. Samples were prepared as self-supporting wafers using a Trystom H-62 hydraulic press at up to 40 MPa, with a mass-to-surface ratio of 8–12 g/cm². Prior to analysis, samples were activated under vacuum (5×10^{-6} Torr) using the same conditions as before the catalytic tests (450 °C, 1 °C/min, 4 h) to ensure that the acid sites detected under these conditions are directly comparable to those present during the catalytic studies. Liquid-phase probe molecules, Py and DTBPy, were adsorbed from the vapor phase at 150 °C for 20 min, under 3.5 Torr (Py) or equilibrium vapor pressure (DTBPy). Solid-phase TTBPy was adsorbed at 170 °C by placing 1 g of TTBPy in a 100 mL glass saturator upstream of the IR cell, heated to 170 °C to generate vapor, which contacted the activated zeolites for 60 min. Following adsorption, samples were treated under vacuum to remove physisorbed probe molecules at 150 °C for 20 min (Py), 150 °C for 60 min (DTBPy), 170 °C for 60 min (TTBPy). Acid site concentrations were calculated using molar absorption coefficients and protocols from Ref. [43] for Py and Ref. [44] for DTBPy and TTBPy. To assess acid strength, thermodesorption was carried out by stepwise heating at 250 °C, 350 °C, and 450 °C for 20 min (Py) or 60 min (DTBPy and TTBPy). The strength of BAS was estimated based on the fraction of acid sites that retained probe molecules (Py for overall acidity, and DTBPy or TTBPy for surface acidity) at 450 °C (Py) and 350 °C (DTBPy and TTBPy). For that, the intensity of the characteristic bands at 350 or 450 °C was related to that at 150 °C as reported in [45].

Determination of the strength and concentration of acid sites was also carried out by potentiometric titration using an Easy pH titrator (Metler-Toledo, Switzerland). For this purpose, 0.2 g of a zeolite catalyst was activated at 450 °C (1 °C/min) for 4 h, cooled down to ambient temperature in a desiccator, and dispersed in 0.1 M NaNO₃ solution (25 mL) with subsequent purging with argon for 15 min in order to

remove carbon dioxide. The titration procedures were performed with 0.1 M NaOH (in 0.1 M NaNO₃) titrant in an automatic mode under Ar media with a minimal titrant portion of 50 µl. The strength of acid sites was calculated using the Gran method [30,46,47].

²⁷Al MAS NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE III HD spectrometer operating at the ²⁷Al Larmor frequency of 130.4 MHz for a 11.7 T magnet. Samples were packed in 2.5-mm zirconium rotors spinning at 20 kHz. A single 0.77-µs radiofrequency pulse provided a non-selective excitation of the ²⁷Al magnetization with a nominal 30° flip angle. The spectra were acquired in 34000–69000 scans with the interscan delay of 0.6 s, the total acquisition time being 6–11 h per spectrum, depending on the sample. Multi-component analysis of the centerband regions of the spectra was performed within the extended Czjzek (EC) model [48] using the fitting program ssNake [49]. Four spectral components were involved to achieve an adequate fit – two positioning at ~0 ppm (assigned to AlO₆) and other two at ~60 ppm (assigned to AlO₄ species). The EC model was chosen to account for the observed positive skewness of ²⁷Al NMR peaks, which is characteristic of a random distribution of the electric-field gradient around the quadrupolar nuclei.

2.3. Catalytic tests

All catalysis experiments were carried out under atmospheric pressure at 60 °C on a multi-experimental workstation StarFish with magnetic stirring of 400 RPM. The catalytic materials were used in the form of fine powders. Before catalytic tests, 100 mg of the zeolite catalyst was activated at 450 °C (1 °C/min) for 4 h to evacuate possible guest molecules that may bind to the acid sites in the zeolite pores. Typically, mesitylene (15 mL, 108 mmol), internal standard (dodecane, 0.2 g), and catalyst (100 mg) were added to a three-neck 25 mL flask equipped with a thermometer and a condenser and heated. Benzyl alcohol (2.5 mmol) was added to the flask when the required temperature was reached. The samples of reaction mixture were taken periodically and analyzed using a gas chromatography instrument (Agilent 8860) equipped with a HP-5 column (30 m length, 320 µm thickness, 0.25 µm film thickness) and an FID detector. A 43-fold molar excess of mesitylene relative to benzyl alcohol was used, as commonly done in Friedel-Crafts alkylation reactions, to suppress side reactions (such as polyalkylation and benzyl alcohol self-condensation). Similar [50,51] or even higher [52] ratios have been employed in previous studies on alkylation of mesitylene with benzyl alcohol.

Conversion of benzyl alcohol (X), yield (Y) and selectivity (S) of targeted C-alkylation product were calculated after 24 h time-on-stream according to the following equations:

$$X (\%) = \frac{[n(\text{benzyl alcohol})_0 - n(\text{benzyl alcohol})_{24}] / n(\text{benzyl alcohol})_0}{n(\text{benzyl alcohol})_0} * 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Y (\%) = \frac{[n(\text{product})_{24} / n(\text{reactant})_0]}{n(\text{benzyl alcohol})_0} * 100 \quad (2)$$

$$S (\%) = \frac{[Y/X]}{1} * 100 \quad (3)$$

where $n(\text{benzyl alcohol})_0$ and $n(\text{benzyl alcohol})_{24}$ are the amounts of the reactant in the reaction mixture initially and after 24 h; $n(\text{product})_{24}$ is the amount of the C-alkylation product formed after 24 h. $n(\text{benzyl alcohol})$ values in Eq. 1 and 2 were determined based on the internal standard calibration method, using commercially available benzyl alcohol (>99.9 %, Sigma Aldrich) and dodecane (≥ 99 %, Sigma Aldrich). The amount of commercially unavailable C-alkylation product, $n(\text{product})$, was estimated using the concept of effective carbon number [53]. Selectivity values were compared at benzyl alcohol conversion of 8 %.

Blank experiments showed no benzyl alcohol conversion or product formation after 24 h in the absence of a catalyst.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural characteristics of nanolayered zeolites FER, MFI, MOR, BEA

In line with literature data and our previous investigations [12,18], SDA2 led to the formation of nanolayered MFI-type zeolite in a wide range of Si/Al ratios in the reaction mixture. In contrast, SDA1 promoted the formation of various zeolites, such as MFI, MOR, BEA and FER [15]. The formation of zeolite of a specific topology was influenced by the Si/Al ratio in the reaction mixture. For instance, MFI-type zeolite was formed at Si/Al ratios of 20 – 30 (Fig. 1). In turn, at lower Si/Al ratios (8–20), MOR or a mixture of MOR and MFI zeolites were obtained. Nanolayered BEA zeolites were synthesized within a narrow Si/Al range of 10–20, particularly when aluminium sulphate was used as the aluminium source. Increasing the Na⁺ content at a fixed Si/Al ratio led to the formation of FER-type zeolite. Further increase in Na⁺ concentration promoted the formation of a mixture of FER and MOR zeolites or a MOR-type zeolite. It is worth noting that FER-type zeolites have previously been synthesized using piperidine [54] and 1,6-bis (N-methylpyrrolidinium)hexane [55] as SDAs. The formation of nanolayered FER in the presence of SDA1 which contains 4,4'-trimethylenebis(1-methylpiperidine) moiety, is in line with the positive structure-directing role of the piperidine fragment in promoting FER-type zeolite crystallization.

All in all, the formation of zeolites of different structural types in the presence of SDA1 was sensitive to the composition of the reaction mixtures and occurred in a rather narrow concentration range of Si and Al sources and NaOH (Fig. 1). As can be seen from the ternary diagram, the regions of MFI and MOR zeolite formation are characterized by a relatively low content of sodium hydroxide (0.16 – 0.18 and 0.18 – 0.21 mol% of Na₂O, respectively) and differ primarily in the content of the aluminium source (0.02 – 0.04 and 0.04 – 0.08 mol%, respectively). However, FER and BEA type zeolites are formed in a quite narrow concentration range of the aluminum source (0.04 ± 0.005 mol%) when balancing Na/Si ratio. Deviation from the optimal concentrations of the initial components results in the formation of mixed phases, the appearance of an amorphous phase or dense non-zeolitic silica phases.

BEA, MOR, and FER zeolites synthesized with SDA1 showed nano-sheet crystal morphology and hierarchical micro-mesoporous character (*vide infra*), but MFI zeolite samples prepared with the same SDA1 formed bulk crystals. Therefore, a nanolayered MFI sample prepared with SDA2 was used for further topology-acidity-activity studies.

Fig. 1. Phase diagram depicting the products obtained as a function of the reaction mixture composition (Si/SDA1 = 16.6 – 30; 150 °C, ~60 rpm, 10–14 days).

XRD patterns of the prepared nanolayered zeolites (Fig. 2a) show characteristic diffraction lines of the respective crystalline materials [31] and no additional signals, confirming structural identity and phase purity of samples synthesized using Gemini-type SDA-assisted crystallization. Nanolayered FER displays diagnostic reflections at $2\theta = 9.3^\circ$ (d_{200}), 12.7° (d_{101}), 13.3° (d_{011}) and 15.2° (d_{310}). Nanolayered MFI shows characteristic peaks at 7.8° (d_{011}), 8.7° (d_{020}), 8.9° (d_{200}), 23.1° (d_{501}), and 23.7° (d_{151}). Nanolayered MOR is identified by reflections at 6.5° (d_{110}), 8.6° (d_{020}), 9.8° (d_{200}), and 13.4° (d_{111}), 13.9° (d_{130}), 15.3° (d_{310}). Nanolayered BEA exhibits fewer, broader reflections at 7.5° (d_{110}) and 22.4° (d_{311}), which is attributed to its ultrathin layer structure (*vide infra*).

SEM images (Fig. 3, left side) of the prepared zeolites reveal a distinct layer morphology, atypical for bulk analogues [56–59]. The planar crystal dimensions vary from ca. 500 nm for BEA and MFI to 1–3 μm for FER and MOR. STEM imaging (Fig. 3, right side) further highlights differences in nanolayered crystals of the studied zeolites. FER sample forms well-ordered nanosheet stacks with a uniform thickness of ca. 10–15 nm, which consist of dozen layers. Similarly to FER, MOR displayed stacked nanosheets, but with a greater thickness of ca. 30–40 nm. Occasionally, ultrathin sheets (<2 nm) appeared at the edges of these stacks, likely indicating incomplete layer growth or localized delamination. In contrast, BEA and MFI show extremely thin loosely organized layers without the dense stacking seen in FER and MOR. This morphology is consistent with the low-intensity diffraction lines of the BEA sample in the XRD pattern (Fig. 2a), indicating the presence of small crystalline domains.

Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms of nanolayered zeolites are typical of materials that combine micro- and mesopores (Fig. 2b). A pronounced uptake and hysteresis loop in the p/p_s region of 0.4–0.9 indicate mesopore formation. The total pore volume ranges from 0.55 to $0.80\text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$, while the micropore volumes calculated using the t -plot method (Fig. SI-1, left) increase in the order $\text{BEA} < \text{MFI} < \text{MOR} \approx \text{FER}$, from 0.02 to $0.12\text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ (Fig. 2b). The area of intercrystalline void volumes follows the same trend, increasing from 263 to $700\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. The nanolayered BEA sample exhibits an exceptionally low V_{micro} value of $0.02\text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$, which can be attributed to the high fraction of surface-exposed pore mouths and the correspondingly low proportion of pores fully embedded within the zeolite framework. These micropore mouths exhibit significantly reduced adsorption potential, approaching that of mesopores, and therefore contribute minimally to nitrogen physisorption-based micropore volume. A similarly low value of V_{micro} has been reported for lamellar ITQ-6 zeolites with FER topology [60].

All samples exhibit a broad mesopore size distribution (Fig. SI-1, right), attributed to intercrystalline voids in aggregated arrays of ultrathin nanolayers.

3.2. Acidic characteristics of and state of Al in nanolayered zeolites FER, MFI, MOR, BEA

The nature and strength distribution of acid sites in nanolayered zeolites were first evaluated by *in situ* FTIR spectroscopy of adsorbed pyridine (Fig. SI-2, Fig. 4), a well-established method for distinguishing and quantifying Brønsted and Lewis acid sites and assessing their strength [43,61]. Also, potentiometric titration was employed to quantify overall acid strength in terms of pK_a (Fig. 5), as detailed in our previous studies [30,46,47]. To selectively probe surface Brønsted acid sites (BAS), adsorption of bulky base molecules monitored with FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. SI-3 and SI-4) was employed [44]. Specifically, DTBPy, which is too bulky to enter the micropores of FER and MFI [62], and TTBPY, previously demonstrated as a selective probe molecule for external BAS in large-pore zeolites [44], such as MOR and BEA, were used to characterize the external acid sites of the respective samples.

The total BAS concentration, estimated from Py adsorption at 150°C , increases in the sequence: BEA (0.11 mmol/g) $<<$ FER (0.20 mmol/g) \approx MOR (0.21 mmol/g) $<$ MFI (0.26 mmol/g ; Fig. 4a). In contrast, Lewis acid site (LAS) concentrations are similar across studied zeolites (0.10 – 0.11 mmol/g , Fig. 4b). The overall strength of BAS, expressed as the fraction of sites retaining Py at 450°C , follows the trend: FER (46 %) $>$ MOR (17 %) $>$ MFI (8 %) $>$ BEA (3 %).

Potentiometric titration revealed several well-defined inflection points, while the first derivative of the titration curves shows 4 maxima (Fig. 5). For example, Gran plot analysis ($10^{-\text{pH} \times V}$ vs. V) for FER enables identification of 3 distinct acid site types with pK_{a1} values of 3.3 (pK_{a1}), 4.8 (pK_{a2}), and 6.6 (pK_{a3}) which are associated with BAS and LAS, and another type of the weak acid sites with $\text{pK}_a \sim 9.0$ – 9.2 (pK_{a4}), likely associated with silanol groups. Among the strongest acid sites, FER exhibits the lowest $\text{pK}_{a1} = 3.3$, followed by MOR ($\text{pK}_{a1} = 3.6$), MFI ($\text{pK}_{a1} = 4.4$), and BEA ($\text{pK}_{a1} = 4.5$), which corroborates with the pyridine thermodesorption results (Fig. 4a). Notably, thermodesorption studies using DTBPy and TTBPY, which selectively probe surface BAS, revealed similar strength of BAS in the range 38–41 % for zeolites with different topologies, suggesting that surface acidity strength is independent on zeolite topology and highlighting the non-transferability of FTIR-Py and potentiometric titration results from bulk to surface acid site analysis. The experimental trend in BAS strength across $\text{FER} > \text{MOR} > \text{MFI}$

Fig. 2. XRD patterns (a) and nitrogen ad-/desorption isotherms (b) of nanolayered zeolites prepared using Gemini-type surfactants. Micropore volume (cm^3/g) and area of intercrystalline mesopores (m^2/g) are shown in figure (b) for respective zeolites.

Fig. 3. SEM (left side) and STEM (right side) images of nanolayered zeolites prepared using Gemini-type surfactants.

> BEA, as derived from pyridine thermodesorption and potentiometric titration, aligns with theoretical predictions of better stabilization of the conjugated base in sterically constrained micropore environments [63]. Furthermore, the experimental observation that surface BAS strength is largely topology-independent likely reflects the balance between intrinsic acidity and reduced stabilization of the conjugate base in non-confined environments due to diminished dispersion interactions.

The coordination environment of Al atoms in nanolayered zeolites of different topologies was analyzed based on ^{27}Al NMR spectra (Fig. 6). The spectra are dominated by a signal from tetrahedrally coordinated framework AlO_4 species (centered at 50 – 60 ppm), with a minor

contribution from octahedral extra-framework AlO_6 species (~ 0 ppm). Compared to their microcrystalline counterparts (Fig. 6, right), nanolayered zeolites (Fig. 6, left) exhibit significant broadening of the framework Al peak, as evidenced by increased peak width at half-height. This trend, previously observed for nanocrystalline zeolites [64] reflects enhanced quadrupolar interactions arising from local distortions of the AlO_4 tetrahedra and elevated electric field gradients at the surface. To understand if and how the zeolite topology influenced the coordination environment of Al atoms, the spectra were normalized by area and deconvoluted into 4 components using a consistent set of quadrupolar coupling constants, asymmetry parameters, and relative intensities

Fig. 4. Concentration of pyridine interacting with Brønsted (a) and Lewis (b) acid sites vs. the desorption temperature (150 – 450 °C) for the nanolayered zeolites prepared using Gemini-type surfactants. Shaded columns in (a) show the results obtained for 2,6-di-*tert*-butylpyridine (for FER and MFI) and 2,4,6-tri-*tert*-butylpyridine (for MOR and BEA). The percentage values indicate the overall fraction of strong acid sites (in blue) and the fraction of strong surface acid sites (in black and white).

Fig. 5. Potentiometric titration curve and its analysis for FER (a) and comparison of the titration profiles for the studied nanolayered zeolites (b).

(Table SI-1): 1) tetra-narrow (corresponding to Al atoms in symmetrical Td coordination, pink component in Fig. 6), tetra-broad (distorted Td, green component in Fig. 6), octa-narrow (symmetrical Oh, violet component in Fig. 6), octa-broad (distorted Oh, orange component in Fig. 6). Notably, the structural changes across nanosheet samples have not much effect on the octahedral Al components mostly affecting the fraction of distorted tetrahedral Al sites. The fraction increases in the sequence MFI (21 %) < FER (30 %) < MOR (57 %) < BEA (64 %) (Table S1) thereby correlating with their external intercrystalline area (Fig. 2b). At the same time, the total fractions of tetrahedrally coordinated Al atoms remain comparable across the samples, varying only within 10 %.

In the first approximation, the ratio of ‘tetra-broad’ to (‘tetra-broad’+‘tetra-narrow’) signals reflects the fraction of framework aluminum in a distorted Td environment. Such distortions likely occur

on the surface of zeolite nanolayers as suggested by a clear correlation observed between the fraction of Al in distorted Td coordination and the mesopore area of the nanolayered zeolites (Fig. 7a).

In addition, zeolite topology seems to determine the distribution of Al atoms among symmetrical and distorted Td coordination. Indeed, among the studied zeolites, BEA exhibits the highest fraction of distorted framework Al atoms (64 %, Fig. 7a), while MFI shows the lowest one (21 %).

To quantify the effect of hierarchical zeolite structure on the Al environment, the fraction of distorted framework Al atoms was plotted against key structural characteristics, such as framework density (FD_{Si}), accessible volume (i.e., a void volume fraction) and a maximum pore diameter (defined as the largest sphere that can fit or diffuse along the zeolite micropores, Fig. 7b). Fig. 7b illustrates the pronounced dependence of aluminum distortion among symmetric and distorted Td

Fig. 6. ^{27}Al NMR spectra of nanolayered and conventional zeolites of variable topologies.

coordination on the framework density and accessible volume, suggesting that more open zeolite frameworks favor the larger fraction of surface aluminum atoms with distorted oxygen environment. On the other hand, the influence of pore diameter on Al state is less pronounced, likely due to the cumulative effect of micro- and mesoporosity, with mesoporosity playing a more significant role in enabling flexible Al coordination.

The tendency of surface aluminum atoms to adopt distorted tetrahedral oxygen environment likely results from a combination of structural factors discussed above. Another key factor, according to [64], is the nanolayer thickness of each of the studied zeolites. Considering that the maximum $\text{N}^+ - \text{N}^+$ distance in SDA1 and SDA2 is about 0.75 and 1.5 nm, respectively, and that zeolite crystallization takes place in the hydrophilic region of the lamellar micelle (with structural breaks in the

Fig. 7. Fraction of distorted framework Al atoms on the mesopore surface area (a) and structural or pore characteristics (b) of nanolayered zeolites: FDSi, T/1000 Å³ (grey); accessible volume, % (green); fitting sphere, Å (red); diffusing sphere, Å (blue).

hydrophobic region), the nanolayer thickness can be estimated as follows: 1.0 – 1.4 nm for MOR, FER, and BEA, and 1.8 – 2.3 nm for MFI (SDA2 contains three N⁺ groups instead of two). In line with this consideration and previous reports [64], the thicker nanolayers of MFI lead to a 1.5–3-fold decrease in the fraction of aluminum atoms in distorted environments (0.21 for MFI compared with 0.30 – 0.63 for other nanolayered zeolites, Fig. 7).

Such distortions of tetrahedral aluminum atoms at the surface of zeolite nanolayers may modulate BASs due to variation in the valence angle ≡Al–O(H)–Si≡ and impact the catalytic performance in surface acid site-sensitive reactions, such as C-benylation of mesitylene, discussed further.

3.3. Catalytic performance of nanolayered zeolites of different topologies in C-benylation of mesitylene

Alkylation of mesitylene with benzyl alcohol (BA) is a convenient reaction that allows to evaluate the activity of acid sites located on the mesopores surface or external surface, since bulky C-alkylation product does not tend to form within zeolite micropores [65–68]. The desired product of the reaction is bulky 1,3,5-trimethyl-2-benzyl-benzene (TMBB), while competing self-etherification of BA produces dibenzyl ether (Scheme 2). Both transformations are predominantly catalyzed by BASs, although LASs may contribute to a lesser extent [39,69–71].

Given small contribution of LAS in the studied reactions and that the concentration of LAS was comparable across the studied nanolayered

Scheme 2. Acid-catalyzed transformations occurring in mesitylene and benzyl alcohol mixture.

zeolites (Figure 4b), differences in catalytic behavior were analyzed in relation to Brønsted acidity. At similar BA conversion of 8 %, the selectivity toward TMBB ranged from 67 % to 84 %, showing no clear correlation with BAS density in nanolayered zeolite catalysts (Figure SI-5). This result suggests that under the applied reaction conditions, competitive adsorption of BA and mesitylene on active sites and neighbor-site proximity effects are unlikely to be the primary factors governing product distribution. No correlation was either observed between TMBB yield and the total BAS concentration (mmol/g) or density ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$) (Figure SI-6, a), the total concentration or density of strong BAS (Figure SI-6, b), the concentration or density of surface BAS (Figure SI-6, c) in the studied nanolayered zeolites. In contrast, both BA conversion and TMBB yield increased with the concentration or density of surface-accessible strong BAS in the sequence: MOR < MFI < FER (Figure 8).

These findings suggest that the BA conversion proceeds predominantly on strong BAS located on the external surface or in mesopores, rather than within micropores. The observed trend is consistent with a Langmuir-Hinshelwood-type rate law, previously reported for the liquid-phase Friedel-Crafts benzylation of mesitylene [72], where a higher density of accessible BAS per unit surface area increases the number of active site-reactant pairs available for the surface reaction. Interestingly, a decrease in performance was observed for the nanolayered BEA catalyst despite its relatively high BAS density (Figure 4a). This suggests that factors beyond acid site density or strength, such as structural distortions or framework-specific site accessibility, may also influence catalytic performance. Notably, the least active catalysts, MOR and BEA, displayed the highest fraction of distorted tetrahedral Al sites, as revealed by ^{27}Al MAS NMR. Previous studies have postulated that the external surface structure of nanolayered MFI and MWW zeolites governs the activity and selectivity of their external BAS in the conversion of benzyl alcohol in mesitylene [50]. In turn, our results point to a potential link between framework distortion, acid site environment, and modulated catalytic efficiency, emphasizing the importance of topology-dependent acid site distribution and accessibility in governing the reactivity of nanolayered zeolites.

Among hierarchical zeolites studied in this work, nanolayered FER demonstrated the best catalytic performance, reaching the BA conversion of 43 % and TMBB selectivity of 84 %. Several previous studies have also reported the benefits of hierarchical zeolites, including layered ones, for the alkylation of aromatics with BA [65,73]. Specifically mesoporous MFI-type zeolites (ranging from ultrathin nanosheets to compact stacked plates) exhibited significantly higher catalytic activity in the alkylation of mesitylene with benzyl alcohol compared to

conventional ZSM-5 (up to ca. 50 % and 10 % BA conversion, respectively) [65]. Application of bolaform surfactants and different Si/Al ratios enabled the synthesis of mesoporous MFI zeolites with various morphologies, including nanosheets, house-of-cards-like structures, and nanosponges [73]. Among these, nanosheets exhibited the highest catalytic activity, achieving complete conversion with up to ca. 50 % selectivity. The present work clearly demonstrates the possibility of the improvement of catalytic activity of hierarchical zeolite by varying their topology (e.g., FER vs. the mostly studied layered MFI).

4. Conclusions

Optimized Gemini-type surfactant-assisted synthesis enabled the preparation of nanolayered hierarchical zeolites with FER, MFI, MOR, and BEA topologies. The formation of each topology was highly sensitive to the synthesis parameters, especially the Si/Al and Na/Si ratios. Nanolayers of BEA and MFI were isolated, while those of FER and MOR assembled into stacked nanosheets. The resulting zeolites exhibited intercrystalline mesopore surface areas up to 230–700 m^2/g . Brønsted acid sites located on the external surfaces of nanolayered zeolites showed weaker interaction with basic probe molecules compared to internal sites due to the lack of confinement effect, while thermodesorption studies revealed similar topology-independent strength of surface Brønsted acid centers. The fraction of distorted tetrahedral Al sites increased with external surface area and was zeolite topology-dependent: MFI (21 %) < FER (30 %) < MOR (57 %) < BEA (64 %).

In catalytic alkylation of mesitylene with benzyl alcohol, a clear correlation was observed between catalytic activity and the concentration (mmol/g) or density (mmol/m^2) of surface-accessible Brønsted acid sites in nanolayered MFI, FER, and MOR, with FER showing the highest yield (37 %) and selectivity (84 %). This trend was disrupted in BEA, which, despite the reasonably high surface Brønsted acid site concentration, showed lower activity. Considering the high fraction of distorted Al sites in BEA, these findings point to the influence of framework-specific structural distortions on catalytic performance of nanolayered zeolites.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jiří Čejka: Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Mariya V. Shamzhy:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Oleksiy V. Shvets:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Mykhailo M. Kurmach:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Michal Mazur:**

Fig. 8. Variation of BA conversion and TMBB yield as a function of the strong surface BAS concentration and density. The numbers in the brackets show the fraction of Al atoms in distorted Td environment.

Investigation, Formal analysis. **Oleg Petrov:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nataliya D. Shcherban:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Petr Golis:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Pavlo S. Yaremov:** Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Given his role as Managing Guest Editor, J. Čejka had no involvement in the peer review of this article and had no access to information regarding its peer review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to another journal editor. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge Dr. S. Samanta for *in situ* FTIR spectroscopic experiments on TTPy thermodesorption. O.S., M.K., N.S. thank the National Research Foundation of Ukraine for the project “Creation of new bifunctional zeolite catalysts for one-pot cascade processes of conversion of platform molecules from biomass into fuels and industrially valuable organic compounds” (project number 2023.03/0139). M.M., J.Č., M.S. thank ERDF/ESF for the project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587). The work of P.G. and O.P. was supported by the Ministry of Education Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic through ERC CZ project LL 2104. N. S. is grateful to the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine for a personal scholarship for young scientists – doctors of sciences for 2024. The authors acknowledge Charles University Centre of Advanced Materials (CUCAM—OP VVV Excellent Research Teams, no. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/15_003/0000417) for providing instrumental facilities enabling this research.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115580](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115580).

Data availability

All data are available in Zenodo open archive under the link: <https://zenodo.org/records/15751171>

References

- J. Čejka, A. Vondrová, B. Wichterlová, G. Vorbeck, R. Fricke, The effect of Al, Fe, and substitution in the MFI silicate structure on the aromatic hydrocarbon transformation: Si-OH-M site strength, *Zeolites* 14 (1994) 147–153.
- M. Shamzhy, M. Opanasenko, P. Concepción, A. Martínez, New trends in tailoring active sites in zeolite-based catalysts, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 48 (2019) 1095–1149.
- A. Primo, H. García, Zeolites as catalysts in oil refining, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 43 (2014) 7548–7561.
- D. Kerstens, B. Smeyers, J. Van Waeyenberg, Q. Zhang, J. Yu, B.F. Sels, State of the art and perspectives of hierarchical zeolites: practical overview of synthesis methods and use in catalysis, *Adv. Mater. (Weinh. Ger.)* 32 (2020) 2004690.
- M. Hartmann, M. Thommes, W. Schwieger, Hierarchically-Ordered zeolites: a critical assessment, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* 8 (2021) 2001841.
- J. Čejka, R. Millini, M. Opanasenko, D.P. Serrano, W.J. Roth, Advances and challenges in zeolite synthesis and catalysis, *Catal. Today* 345 (2020) 2–13.
- C.J. Heard, J. Čejka, M. Opanasenko, P. Nachtigall, G. Centi, S. Perathoner, 2D oxide nanomaterials to address the energy transition and catalysis, *Adv. Mater. (Weinh. Ger.)* 31 (2019) 1801712.
- W.J. Roth, M. Opanasenko, M. Mazur, B. Gil, J. Čejka, T. Sasaki, Current state and perspectives of exfoliated zeolites, *Adv. Mater. (Weinh. Ger.)* 36 (2024) 2307341.
- N. Hijazi, A. Bavykina, I. Yarulina, T. Shoinchorova, E.V. Ramos-Fernandez, J. Gascon, Chemical engineering of zeolites: alleviating transport limitations through hierarchical design and shaping, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1035cs00169b>.
- M. Shamzhy, B. Gil, M. Opanasenko, W.J. Roth, J. Čejka, MWW and MFI frameworks as model layered zeolites: structures, transformations, properties, and activity, *ACS Catal.* 11 (2021) 2366–2396.
- G.T.M. Kadja, N.J. Azhari, S. Mardiana, N.T.U. Culsum, A. Maghfirah, Recent advances in the development of nanosheet zeolites as heterogeneous catalysts, *Results Eng.* 17 (2023) 100910.
- M. Choi, K. Na, J. Kim, Y. Sakamoto, O. Terasaki, R. Ryoo, Stable single-unit-cell nanosheets of zeolite MFI as active and long-lived catalysts, *Nature* 461 (2009) 246–249.
- B.-T.L. Bleken, D.S. Wragg, B. Arstad, A.E. Gunnæs, J. Mouzon, S. Helveg, L. F. Lundegaard, P. Beato, S. Bordiga, U. Olsbye, S. Svelle, K.P. Lillerud, Unit cell thick nanosheets of zeolite H-ZSM-5: structure and activity, *Top. Catal.* 56 (2013) 558–566.
- R. Kore, R. Srivastava, B. Satpati, Synthesis of industrially important aromatic and heterocyclic ketones using hierarchical ZSM-5 and beta zeolites, *Appl. Catal. A* 493 (2015) 129–141.
- J.E. Sánchez-Velandia, M. Kurmach, O. Shvets, H.G. Baldoví, E. García-Verdugo, D. Y. Murzin, N. Shcherban, Fine-Tuning of acidity in hierarchical zeolites for the efficient prins cyclization yielding florol, *ACS Sust. Chem. Eng.* 12 (2024) 16283–16296.
- F.M. Menger, C.A. Littau, Gemini-surfactants: synthesis and properties, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 113 (1991) 1451–1452.
- K. Na, C. Jo, J. Kim, K. Cho, J. Jung, Y. Seo, R.J. Messinger, B.F. Chmelka, R. Ryoo, Directing zeolite structures into hierarchically nanoporous architectures, *Science* 333 (2011) 328–332.
- O.V. Shvets, K.M. Konyshva, M.V. Shamzhy, M.V. Opanasenko, P.S. Yaremov, C. Xiao, X. Zou, J. Čejka, Mordenite nanorods and nanosheets prepared in presence of gemini type surfactants, *Catal. Today* 324 (2019) 115–122.
- M.-T. Yuan, D.-Y. Zhao, Q.-Q. Hao, Q.-X. Luo, J. Zhang, H. Chen, M. Sun, L. Xu, X. Ma, Gemini Surfactant-Directed facile pillaring of Two-Dimensional zeolites with enhanced catalytic activity in Friedel–Crafts alkylation, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 59 (2020) 16312–16320.
- K. Lu, J. Huang, L. Ren, C. Li, Y. Guan, B. Hu, H. Xu, J. Jiang, Y. Ma, P. Wu, High ethylene selectivity in Methanol-to-Olefin (MTO) reaction over MOR-Zeolite nanosheets, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 59 (2020) 6258–6262.
- Y. Liu, N. Zhao, H. Xian, Q. Cheng, Y. Tan, N. Tsubaki, X. Li, Facilely synthesized H-Mordenite nanosheet assembly for carbonylation of dimethyl ether, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 7 (2015) 8398–8403.
- K. Saenluang, T. Imyen, W. Wannapakdee, D. Suttitip, P. Dugkhuntod, M. Ketkaew, A. Thivavasith, C. Wattanakit, Hierarchical nanospherical ZSM-5 nanosheets with uniform al distribution for alkylation of benzene with ethanol, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 3 (2020) 3252–3263.
- Y. Zhou, Y. Mu, M.-F. Hsieh, B. Kabius, C. Pacheco, C. Bator, R.M. Rioux, J. D. Rimer, Enhanced surface activity of MWW zeolite nanosheets prepared via a One-Step synthesis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 142 (2020) 8211–8222.
- S. Gutiérrez-Rubio, M. Shamzhy, J. Čejka, D.P. Serrano, I. Moreno, J.M. Coronado, Vapor phase acylation of guaiacol with acetic acid over micro, nano and hierarchical MFI and BEA zeolites, *Appl. Catal. B* 285 (2021) 119826.
- J. Kim, W. Park, R. Ryoo, Surfactant-Directed zeolite nanosheets: a High-Performance catalyst for Gas-Phase beckmann rearrangement, *ACS Catal.* 1 (2011) 337–341.
- M.V. Opanasenko, M.V. Shamzhy, C. Jo, R. Ryoo, J. Čejka, Annulation of phenols: catalytic behavior of conventional and 2 d zeolites, *ChemCatChem* 6 (2014) 1919–1927.
- N. Shcherban, R. Barakov, B. Lasne, P. Mäki-Arvela, M. Shamzhy, I. Bezverkhyy, J. Wörnå, D.Y. Murzin, Florol synthesis via prins cyclization over hierarchical beta zeolites, *Mol. Catal.* 531 (2022) 112683.
- Y. Seo, K. Cho, Y. Jung, R. Ryoo, Characterization of the surface acidity of MFI zeolite nanosheets by ³¹P NMR of adsorbed phosphine oxides and catalytic cracking of decalin, *ACS Catal.* 3 (2013) 713–720.
- M. Shamzhy, J. Prech, J. Zhang, V. Ruaux, H. El-Siblani, S. Mintova, Quantification of lewis acid sites in 3D and 2D TS-1 zeolites: FTIR spectroscopic study, *Catal. Today* 345 (2020) 80–87.
- O.V. Shvets, M.M. Kurmach, K.M. Konyshva, O.I. Lozovytka, N.D. Shcherban, Evaluation of acidity of hierarchical zeolites using a potentiometric titration method, *Mater. Today Chem.* 36 (2024) 101921.
- C. Baerlocher, L.B. McCusker, D.H. Olson. Atlas of Zeolite Framework Types, ed 6, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2007.
- L.B. McCusker, F. Liebau, G. Engelhardt, Nomenclature of structural and compositional characteristics of ordered microporous and mesoporous materials with inorganic hosts (IUPAC recommendations 2001), *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 58 (2003) 3–13.
- A. Corma, Inorganic solid acids and their use in Acid-Catalyzed hydrocarbon reactions, *Chem. Rev. (Wash. DC U. S.)* 95 (1995) 559–614.
- A. Corma, From microporous to mesoporous molecular sieve materials and their use in catalysis, *Chem. Rev. (Wash. DC U. S.)* 97 (1997) 2373–2420.
- M. Boronat, A. Corma, What is measured when measuring acidity in zeolites with probe molecules? *ACS Catal.* 9 (2019) 1539–1548.
- K. Cho, K. Na, J. Kim, O. Terasaki, R. Ryoo, Zeolite synthesis using hierarchical Structure-Directing surfactants: retaining porous structure of initial synthesis gel and precursors, *Chem. Mater.* 24 (2012) 2733–2738.
- W. Park, D. Yu, K. Na, K.E. Jelfs, B. Slater, Y. Sakamoto, R. Ryoo, Hierarchically structure-directing effect of multi-ammonium surfactants for the generation of MFI zeolite nanosheets, *Chem. Mater.* 23 (2011) 5131–5137.

- [38] M.V. Shamzhy, O.V. Shvets, M.V. Opanasenko, L. Kurfirtová, D. Kubicka, J. Čejka, Extra-Large-Pore zeolites with UTL topology: control of the catalytic activity by variation in the nature of the active sites, *ChemCatchem* 5 (2013) 1891–1898.
- [39] T. Soták, Z. Magyarová, M. Shamzhy, M. Kubů, K. Gołabek, J. Čejka, M. Hronec, Gas-phase etherification of cyclopentanol with methanol to cyclopentyl methyl ether catalyzed by zeolites, *Appl. Catal. A* 618 (2021) 118122.
- [40] B.C. Lippens, J.H. De Boer, studies on pore systems in catalysts: V. The t method, *J. Catal.* 4 (1965) 319–323.
- [41] S. Brunauer, P.H. Emmett, E. Teller, Adsorption of gases in multimolecular layers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 60 (1938) 309–319.
- [42] E.P. Barrett, L.G. Joyner, P.P. Halenda, The determination of pore volume and area distributions in porous substances. I. computations from nitrogen isotherms, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 73 (1951) 373–380.
- [43] V. Zholobenko, C. Freitas, M. Jendrlin, P. Bazin, A. Travert, F. Thibault-Starzyk, Probing the acid sites of zeolites with pyridine: quantitative AGIR measurements of the molar absorption coefficients, *J. Catal.* 385 (2020) 52–60.
- [44] L. Lakiss, A. Vicente, J.-P. Gilson, V. Valtchev, S. Mintova, A. Vimont, R. Bedard, S. Abdo, J. Bricker, Probing the Brønsted acidity of the external surface of Faujasite-Type zeolites, *ChemPhysChem* 21 (2020) 1873–1881.
- [45] Y. Zhou, A. Galarneau, J. Rodriguez, M. Opanasenko, M. Shamzhy, Correlating mesoporosity/acidity with catalytic performances for surfactant-templated mesoporous FAU zeolites, *Mater. Adv.* 5 (2024) 3207–3219.
- [46] K. Yu, N. Kumar, A. Aho, J. Roine, I. Heinmaa, D.Y. Murzin, A. Ivaska, Determination of acid sites in porous aluminosilicate solid catalysts for aqueous phase reactions using potentiometric titration method, *J. Catal.* 335 (2016) 117–124.
- [47] N.D. Shcherban, S.M. Filonenko, R.Y. Barakov, S.A. Sergiienko, K. Yu, I. Heinmaa, A. Ivaska, D.Y. Murzin, New insights in evaluation of acid sites in micro-mesoporous zeolite-like materials using potentiometric titration method, *Appl. Catal. A* 543 (2017) 34–42.
- [48] G. Czjzek, J. Fink, F. Götz, H. Schmidt, J.M.D. Coey, J.P. Rebouillat, A. Liénard, Atomic coordination and the distribution of electric field gradients in amorphous solids, *Phys. Rev. B* 23 (1981) 2513–2530.
- [49] S.G.J. van Meerten, W.M.J. Franssen, A.P.M. Kentgens, Ssnake: a cross-platform open-source NMR data processing and fitting application, *J. Magn. Reson.* 301 (2019) 56–66.
- [50] D. Liu, X. Zhang, A. Bhan, M. Tsapatsis, Activity and selectivity differences of external Brønsted acid sites of single-unit-cell thick and conventional MFI and MWW zeolites, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 200 (2014) 287–290.
- [51] Y. Wu, Z. Lu, L. Emdadi, S.C. Oh, J. Wang, Y. Lei, H. Chen, D.T. Tran, I.C. Lee, D. Liu, Tuning external surface of unit-cell thick pillared MFI and MWW zeolites by atomic layer deposition and its consequences on acid-catalyzed reactions, *J. Catal.* 337 (2016) 177–187.
- [52] J. Grzybek, W.J. Roth, B. Gil, A. Korzeniowska, M. Mazur, J. Čejka, R.E. Morris, A new layered MWW zeolite synthesized with the bifunctional surfactant template and the updated classification of layered zeolite forms obtained by direct synthesis, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 7 (2019) 7701–7709.
- [53] F.W. Jones, Estimation of flame-ionization detector relative response factors for oligomers of alkyl and aryl ether polyethoxylates using the effective carbon number concept, *J. Chromatogr. Sci.* 36 (1998) 223–226.
- [54] G. Pál-Borbély, H.K. Beyer, Y. Kiyozumi, F. Mizukami, Synthesis and characterization of a ferrierite made by recrystallization of an aluminium-containing hydrated magadiite. Dedicated to professor Iovt V.C. Rees in recognition and appreciation of his lifelong devotion to zeolite science and his outstanding achievements in this field.1, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 22 (1998) 57–68.
- [55] R.K.S. Almeida, L. Gómez-Hortigüela, A.B. Pinar, J. Pérez-Pariente, Synthesis of ferrierite by a new combination of co-structure-directing agents: 1,6-bis(N-methylpyrrolidinium)hexane and tetramethylammonium, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 232 (2016) 218–226.
- [56] W.-g. Kim, X. Zhang, J.S. Lee, M. Tsapatsis, S. Nair, Epitaxially grown layered MFI–Bulk MFI hybrid zeolitic materials, *ACS Nano* 6 (2012) 9978–9988.
- [57] L. Emdadi, D.T. Tran, Y. Wu, S.C. Oh, G. Zhu, I.C. Lee, D. Liu, BEA nanosponge/ultra-thin lamellar MFI prepared in one-step: integration of 3D and 2D zeolites into a composite for efficient alkylation reactions, *Appl. Catal. A* 530 (2017) 56–65.
- [58] J. Ruan, P. Wu, B. Slater, Z. Zhao, L. Wu, O. Terasaki, Structural characterization of interlayer expanded zeolite prepared from ferrierite lamellar precursor, *Chem. Mater.* 21 (2009) 2904–2911.
- [59] P. Sharma, P. Rajaram, R. Tomar, Synthesis and morphological studies of nanocrystalline MOR type zeolite material, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 325 (2008) 547–557.
- [60] M.K. de Pietre, F.A. Bonk, C. Rettori, F.A. Garcia, H.O. Pastore, [V,Al]-ITQ-6: novel porous material and the effect of delamination conditions on v sites and their distribution, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 145 (2011) 108–117.
- [61] S. Bordiga, C. Lamberti, F. Bonino, A. Travert, F. Thibault-Starzyk, Probing zeolites by vibrational spectroscopies, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 44 (2015) 7262–7341.
- [62] A. Corma, V. Fornés, L. Forni, F. Márquez, J. Martínez-Triguero, D. Moscotti, 2,6-Di-Tert-Butyl-Pyridine as a probe molecule to measure external acidity of zeolites, *J. Catal.* 179 (1998) 451–458.
- [63] J. Sauer, Brønsted activity of two-dimensional zeolites compared to bulk materials, *Faraday Discuss.* 188 (2016) 227–234.
- [64] W. Zhang, X. Bao, X. Guo, X. Wang, A high-resolution solid-state NMR study on nano-structured HZSM-5 zeolite, *Catal. Lett.* 60 (1999) 89–94.
- [65] D. Xu, J. Ma, A. Song, Z. Liu, R. Li, Availability and interconnectivity of pores in mesostructured ZSM-5 zeolites by the adsorption and diffusion of mesitylene, *Adsorption* 22 (2016) 1083–1090.
- [66] J. Grzybek, M. Kubů, W.J. Roth, B. Gil, J. Čejka, V. Kasneryk, Structural transformation and chemical modifications of the unusual layered zeolite MWW form SSZ-70, *Catal. Today* 354 (2020) 133–140.
- [67] A. Korzeniowska, J. Grzybek, K. Kałahurska, M. Kubu, W.J. Roth, B. Gil, The structure-catalytic activity relationship for the transient layered zeolite MCM-56 with MWW topology, *Catal. Today* 345 (2020) 116–124.
- [68] K. Ogorzały, G. Jajko, K. Wolski, S. Zapotoczny, M. Kubů, W.J. Roth, B. Gil, W. Makowski, Catalytic activity enhancement in pillared zeolites produced from exfoliated MWW monolayers in solution, *Catal. Today* 390–391 (2022) 272–280.
- [69] C. Perego, P. Ingallina, Recent advances in the industrial alkylation of aromatics: new catalysts and new processes, *Catal. Today* 73 (2002) 3–22.
- [70] M. Milina, S. Mitchell, N.-L. Michels, J. Kenvin, J. Pérez-Ramírez, Interdependence between porosity, acidity, and catalytic performance in hierarchical ZSM-5 zeolites prepared by post-synthetic modification, *J. Catal.* 308 (2013) 398–407.
- [71] S.A. Kadam, M.V. Shamzhy, IR operando study of ethanol dehydration over MFI zeolite, *Catal. Today* 304 (2018) 51–57.
- [72] S. Ezenwa, G.M. Hopping, E.D. Sauer, T. Scott, S. Mack, R. Gounder, Quantification of extracrystalline acid sites in MFI zeolites after post-synthetic passivation treatments using mesitylene benzylation kinetics, *React. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2024) 1096–1112.
- [73] B. Liu, Z. Chen, J. Huang, H. Chen, Y. Fang, Direct synthesis of hierarchically structured MFI zeolite nanosheet assemblies with tailored activity in benzylation reaction, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 273 (2019) 235–242.